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“AGRICULTURE REDEFINED”

Agriculture is considered by many as a way of life especially among those living in the rural areas. Millions of people around the world rely on agriculture as source of food, feed, fiber and fuel. From the early civilizations up to the modern times, agriculture plays a pivotal role in the survival of the human society. It has remained a top priority among local and international leaders in their political and economic agenda. The latest universal framework described as brittle, anxious, non-linear and incomprehensible has brought agriculture into the magnifying lens as it brought new challenge and perspective to “the mother of all industries and the maintainer of human life”. In the context of agriculture education, agriculture remains a term which can be defined or described into four basic units, to wit: Science, Art, Business, and Profession.

As a science. Agriculture is a systematized body knowledge learned through step by step method in the discovery of facts and principles through the formulation of hypothesis, testing of hypothesis, designing of experiments, gathering of facts, analysis and interpretation of facts until a general conclusion and recommendation are arrived which ultimately become a general practice and a law. It has major areas such as Animal Science, Crop Science, Soil Science, Crop Protection, Agricultural Extension and Communication and Agricultural Economics and Marketing. There are also other fields of sciences which contribute to the research, development and innovations in Agriculture.

As an art, Agriculture emphasizes that food production requires skills and practice to generate beauty and pleasant arrangements of plant and animal combination in order to satisfy man’s aspiration and perfection of his environment. There are diverse diverse human activities which involve psycho-motor skills in crop production such plowing, harrowing, furrowing, planting, fertilizing and harvesting. In animal production, some of the practices are breeding, feeding, watering, castrating, and slaughtering. The ability of the agriculturist or farmer to perform these skills depends on the training and experiences acquired. Expertise in the art and techniques of farming will contribute much to the productivity of the farm.

As a business, Agriculture is combined with business as it involves farming, management, production and marketing of agricultural commodities such as livestock and crops. A field in agriculture is known as agribusiness or agricultural business includes resource management, entrepreneurship and sales. Agriculture as a business refers to the activities that put farmers, processors, distributors, and consumers within a system that produces, processes, transports, markets and distributes agricultural products. Agriculture does play an important role in the economy but it also serves as a great source of profit for

entrepreneurs. From rice fields to fishponds and other farm products a farmers can sell to have income, defray farm expenses and gain profit.

As a Profession, the Agriculture sector needs agriculturist who is technically qualified and competent to practice the agriculture profession and who has been issued a certificate of registration and professional license as agriculturist by the Board of Agriculture and the Professional Regulation Commission. These professionals are graduates of a baccalaureate degree program in agriculture from recognized public and private higher education institutions. The practice of the agriculture profession shall refer to the application of known and fundamental principles peculiar to the condition and requirements of agriculture as a field of science, as an industry and/or business which shall include conduct of research and extension, teaching, management and marketing services in the government and private sectors.

The redefinition of Agriculture from the academic point of view provides a more clear understanding of the importance of the sector as the backbone of the Philippine economy. It is grounded with science, manifested with the art, intertwined with the business and practiced as a profession. As we deal with the Internet of Things and confront with the Artificial Intelligence, simple definition of the term Agriculture will guide us to make it more vibrant, by precept and by example.

